

Title: *Transpuan Communities in Bali: Ethnographic Perspectives on Precarity, Resistance, and Queer Joy*

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Abstract:

This paper offers ethnographic insights into the lives of *transpuan* women in Bali, Indonesia, based on fieldwork conducted in 2024–2025. While Bali is often seen as a safe haven for queer people within the Indonesian archipelago, this study uncovers the contradictions within such narratives. Through four case studies—Tasya, Julia, Timo, and Lucinta Luna—the paper examines how *transpuan* navigate intersecting systems of precarity, misrecognition, and resistance.

The research shows how migration to Bali is fueled by both hope and necessity, as *transpuan* seek safer spaces and financial opportunities. However, their experiences are influenced by racialized beauty standards, religious norms, and limited legal recognition. Tasya’s story highlights community care and activism despite marginalization; Julia’s narrative demonstrates how misrecognition can extend into death, influenced by Islamic burial customs; Timo uses social media to educate and empower, challenging common portrayals of trans lives; and Lucinta Luna’s controversial visibility as an influencer complicates ideas of agency and resistance.

Instead of portraying *transpuan* lives only as victims, this paper highlights queer joy as a form of resistance and survival. It advocates for a more nuanced view of *transpuan* identities, guided by intersectional and decolonial perspectives. The research adds to broader LGBTIQ+ discussions by elevating voices from the Global South and challenging dominant narratives that hide the complexity and vibrancy of trans lives.

This research encourages reflection on how queer communities resist erasure, foster solidarity, and reimagine living conditions amid structural violence. It also prompts questions about recognition, visibility, and the politics of representation in Southeast Asia.